

Customer Response towards Google Pay and their Satisfaction Level in Bangalore

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Pradeep, G., et al.
“Customer Response towards Google Pay and Their Satisfaction Level in Bangalore.”
Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 243–52.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575349>

Dr. G. Pradeep

*Associate Professor, Department of PG Studies, Jain College PG Center
V.V Puram, Bangalore*

V. Niveditha

Student 3rd semester M.Com, Jain College PG Center, VV Puram, Bangalore

M. Nusrath Fathima

Student 3rd semester M.Com, Jain College PG centre, VV Puram, Bangalore

Introduction of Google Pay

Google Pay is the simple way to send or receive money with anyone and without any transaction fees. Straight from your bank account to almost anyone. You can send or receive money even if your contact is not in Google Pay.

Money made simple, by Google Pay builds for India with all the features and rewards you love, plus much more. Google Pay is the simplest way to send money home to your family, recharge your mobile, DTH, electricity bill, water bill, post-paid, insurance, Gas bill, data card, municipal tax.

Google Pay covered with easy access to past transactions, so you are always in control. Use it wherever you see UPI or Google Pay. Pay and receive money instantly using your existing bank accounts. No more reloading mobile wallet balances or withdrawal fees. It's your money, made simple.

Google Pay protects your money with a world class security system that helps detect fraud and prevents hacking. Safeguard your account with your screen lock, such as your fingerprint. And if you ever need assistance, Google Pay help centre, phone and chat support are available all day, every day.

Digital Payments in India

Digital payment is a method of transactions in which the payment is made by digital modes. In digital payments, customer and receiver both use digital application to pay and accept money. It is also called electronic payment, which is an instant and convenient method to make payments, and no hard cash is involved in digital payments. All the transactions in digital payments are complete online. It occurs when goods or services are being purchased through the use of various electronic mediums. There is no use of cash or cheques. In a cashless economy, all transactions are carried out using different types of payment methods, and this does not involve the physical use of money for the purchase of various goods and services.

Different types of Digital Payments in India

Digital payment has many kinds of payment, some modes meant for tech-savvies and some for less-technical persons.

- banking cards
- USD
- Aadhaar Enabled Payment System (AEPS)
- UPI
- Mobile Wallet
- Point of Sale (PoS)
- Internet Banking
- Mobile Banking
- Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM) app

Procedure to use Google Pay

1. Open the Google pay app by tapping on its icon.
2. Create an account.
3. Create a 4-digit PIN for your wallet.
4. Open the app menu.
5. Tap the settings option.
6. Add the bank account.
7. Add the debit or credit card.
8. Open the wallet on the home screen.
9. Tap to send the amount.

Swot Analysis of Google Pay

	Positive Factors	Negative Factors
Internal Factors	STRENGTHS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best Prices • Lots of Inventory • Exclusive deal with big name brand • Recently rebuilt website 	WEAKNESSES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive shipping • Lack of most popular product • High CPCs • Generic landing pages
External Factors	OPPORTUNITIES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New advertising channels – Bing, Facebook, YouTube • Implement new conversion tracking 	THREATS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitors increasing marketing budgets • Product declining in popularity according to Google Trends

Statement of the Problem

Research was scarce in the field of contribution of digital payment in reduction of cashless transactions with specific reference to Jain college Bangalore covering the broad umbrella of digital payments in reduction of paper money from the survey cited and hence it is evident no research has taken place in above and mentioned topic, and this paved the way to undertake this particular research in connection with Google pay in reduction of physical payments with specific reference to Bangalore.

Research Gap

In this research, an effort is made to understand the customer preferences through the Google pay, where there was an acute need for undertaking the research.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the customer’s response towards online payment.
- To analyze the trend of respondents towards Google pay.
- To assess the factors influencing the respondents to go to Google pay.
- To provide suitable suggestions and recommendations, if any.

Limitations of the Study

- Time constraint.
- Place constraint.
- Research is confined only to Google pay.

Research Design

1. Data type
 - Primary data.
2. Methods of sampling
 - Simple random sampling.
3. Sample size
 - 100 samples.
4. Sampling technique
 - Questionnaire method.
4. Data type
 - Both qualitative and quantitative data used in this survey.
5. Statistical tools
 - Pie charts and bar diagrams.
6. Mathematical tools
 - Percentages.
7. Research type
 - Empirical research.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. The different age groups of respondents.

10-20	67%
20-30	30%
30-40	3%

Chart Showing the Different Age Group of Respondents

Interpretation for the above Chart

From the above graph, it can be interpreted that the majority of the respondents belong to the age group of 20-25 who are up to 67%, age group of 25-30 who are up to 30%, and remaining 3% belong to the age group of 30-40.

2. Are you aware of Google pay?

Yes	89%
No	11%

Chart Showing the Awareness of Google Pay

Interpretation for the above Chart

From the entire study, it is known that 100 out of 89 respondents are aware of Google pay and 11% of the respondent doesn't know about Google pay.

3. Have you ever used Google pay? why Give reason.

Never heard about Google pay	18%
Concerned about security(don't trust online banking)	40%
Lack of technical skills	18%
All the above	24%

Chart Showing Reasons for not using the Google Pay

Interpretation for the above chart

40% of respondents don't use Google pay only because they are concerned about security (don't trust online banking). And 60% of respondents never heard of Google pay and lack of technical issues. They are worried about using Google pay.

4. From where did you get the information about Google pay?

Social media	35%
Friends/relatives	63%
Magzine	1%
Others	1%

Chart Showing the Analysis of the Information Gathered based on the above Criteria

Interpretation for the above Chart

The majority of 63% respondents come to know about Google pay from their friends and relatives, the other 35% of respondents use Google pay by watching advertisements in social media and 3% know from play store.

5. Which factor is influencing you to use Google Pay?

Simple and convenient	62%
Safe and secure	32%
Better ratings	6%

Chart Showing the Factor Influencing to use Google Pay

Interpretation for the above Chart

The majority of 62% of respondents feel that using Google pay is very simple, and convenient and 33% of respondents use Google pay only because security provided by Google pay is good.

6. For which of the following reason you use Google pay?

Money transfer	31%
Recharge, utility and bill payments	6%
All the above	62%

Chart Showing the Cause of Google Pay

Interpretation for the above Chart

The majority of 62% respondents use Google pay for transferring of money and other 38% for paying recharge, utilities, and for bill payments.

7. What is your opinion use of Google pay in business transactions?

Yes	85%
No	15%

Chart Showing the Number of People Opting for Google Pay in Business Transactions

Interpretation for the above Chart

Of the 100 respondents, 85% of them recommend using Google Pay in their business transactions whereas, 15% of them are not comfortable with it.

8. Are your queries being resolved by Google Pay?

Yes	66%
No	34%

Chart Showing Queries resolved by Google Pay

Interpretation for the above Chart

From the above diagram it can be analyzed that 66% of queries quickly resolved by the Googlepay and the amount which is debited to bank account but not credited to the receiver’s account will be refunded within 72 hours (3days).

9. Which offer attracts you towards Google pay?

Availability of discount	23%
Premium offers	13%
Scratch cards	58%
Others	6%

Chart Showing various Schemes that Attracts the Customer towards Google Pay

Interpretation for the above Chart

Of the respondents, it can be understood that 57% of respondents out of 100 prefer Google pay because they are being attracted to the scratch card and 23% of the respondents prefer Google pay because of the premiums, and discounts and the other 20% have their benefits.

10. What is your opinion about other modes of payment in comparison with Google pay?

Substitute	77%
Supportive instrument	18%
Others	5%

Chart Showing the Opinions of People towards Google Pay in Comparison with other Modes

Interpretation for the above Chart

From the responses received, it can be interpreted that about 77% of respondents prefer Google pay as substitute whereas 18% of respondents use Google pay as a supportive instrument, and 5% for other purposes.

11. The Overall analysis of Google pay

Strongly disagree	9%
Disagree	3%
Agree	70%
Strongly agree	18%

Chart Showing Overall Analysis of Google Pay

Interpretation for the above Chart

From the overall analysis we can know that 70 out of 100 respondents agree that Google pay is a preferable app for online payment of accounts and bills only 1% of respondents are disagreed to use Google pay.

Findings

- To achieve customer satisfaction, Google pay should have to improve in providing a good technical facility for easy access the transactions.
- Customers are tending to use Google pay even though there will be a new technological up-gradation in the future because of its convenience and easy to use.

- The responses taken from 100 respondents gives the inference that people will continue to assess Google pay because of the attractive discounts, offers given by the application.
- From the above research undertaken and responses received from 100 samples we can recommend and suggest that theGoogle pay should increase its advertisement as 11 people out of 100 are not aware of Google pay and the application team has to try to solve the queries better as 34% of the sample are not getting their queries resolved from the backend team.

Conclusion

The objective of this study is to maximize the digital platform, especially Google pay. The “cash mode” on the Google pay uses ultrasonic audio to pair with another Tez user nearby. Though we can say that Google pay stands as a important tool for improvising the economy towards a cashless economy (digitization).The volume of transactions has grown rapidly from 2017 to 2018 drastically. Thus it can be concluded that Google pay helps to the theme of cashless economy and improvising the country towards digitization and economic growth.

Recommendation

- There’s no need to worry about reloading wallets and you don’t need to do additional KYC.
- Using BHIM Unified Payments Interface (UPI), money transfers are simple & secure with Google Pay.
- Respondents should have an Indian bank account with a phone number linked to it to use this version of Google Pay. Google Pay works with all banks in India that support BHIM UPI.
- Conveniently, pay bills Pay for electricity, gas, water, DTH, mobile, and more. You only need to link your biller accounts once to pay your bill with just a few taps.

Bibliography

- <https://pay.google.com>
- <https://www.howtogeek.com>
- www.pocket-lint.com
- <https://www.mastercard.us>
- <https://google-wallet.in.softonic.com>

Questionnaire

Customer response towards Google pay and theirSatisfaction level in Bangalore NUSRATH FATHIMA M and NIVEDITHA V of class 3rd semester M.COM request you to kindly fill in the following questions. Your response would help us to present a paper on, to be presenting on National conference conducted by Jain College on the date. We promise to maintain confidentiality about the information shared by you. Thank you with sincere regards.

1. Name:
2. Age:
3. Are you aware of Google pay?
 - Yes
 - No
4. Have you ever used Google pay why? Give reason
 - Never heard of Google pay
 - Concerned about security (don’t trust online banking)
 - Lack of technical skills
 - All the above

5. From where did you get the information about Google Pay?

- social media
- friends/relatives
- magazine
- Other

6. Which factor is influencing you to use Google Pay?

- Simple and convenient
- Safe and secure
- Better ratings

7. For which of the following reasons you use Google Pay?

- Money transfer
- Recharge, utility and bill payments
- All the above

8. What is your opinion towards the use of Google pay in business?

- Yes
- No

9. Are your queries being resolved by Google pay?

- Yes
- No

10. Which offer attract you towards Google pay?

- Availability of discount
- Premium offers
- Scratch cards
- Other

11. What is your opinion about modes of payments in comparison with Google pay?

- Substitute
- Supportive instrument
- Other

12. The Overall analysis of Google pay.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree